

1/ at'(2)&mpR tEd ajrmuyllftu&mrsmull tajccbf

ylwlonf rrwltolij/aeom ylpum;twuf vltiy/vmaom pmta&tom;ull tEd ajrmuyllfa'o pmta&tom;wlrS tajcc&, bl[efwygon/ talumifrñ yltu&mw\Noif yiftaetxm;rm;onf ajrmuyllft tEd tu&mwEsha, bk soabm waejci, jzplygon/ (armi hmi hq 2010? 7/) atmuygZ, m;(1)ullunlyg/

Z, m(1) jAm[E u&mpwizBzlrESHystu&moif yIEll, Ofi

tu&mrn		celh&umv	tu&myl
(a&stEd) jAm[P		bpl(3)	
ajrmuyllft	rx&m	at'(2)	
	ube	at'(2)	
	*lyA	at'(4)	
(a&sjrefm) ysl		at'(3)	
awmi lyllft	tE&	at'(2)	
	arm&d	at'(3)	
	yv0	at'(4)	

pZ, m;wlf tEd jAm[E u&mw\awmi lyllftajrmuyllft pwiufym;p0uyif obmpñ jcm;em;aom tu&mrsm;ES hEllf, Ofum azmfyxm;ygony/ (armi hmi hq 2010? 8/)

xltjyif Asnf, Of o&a&;om;rl pepfrivnf, Asnf,tu&mwptclul xu? atmu? O? , m rS Asnf, Of o& oaufrsm;, Ofw&ompeptul tolijkxm;ygony/ (armi hmi hq 2009? 3/) Z, m;(2)ullunlyg/

Z, m(2) yslAsnf, Ofb&a&;omrpepf

	t	td	tk	at	atm	th
ysl	—					

azmfyyg taxmuftxm;rm;t& ylwlonf pmta&tom;twwull a&stEd ajrmuyllfta&tom;ull tajcclum wwajrmucMu [efwygon/

2/ rrbmompumtwuf jylyizelwjcifsm

ajrmuyllitEd ta&tomrsmull tajcck, &mw6? tifltn&d eftEG f (azarmiwi? 1958? 31-33/) a&stEd pumwEsh jcmemaeaom yswltwuf tu&m ton/\$ pef Transcription ull &, &mw6f rrbpum,oltm; ull pmjyl&ef rsmptcutl c[elwygon/ (armiarmi&qb 2010? 9/)

xltwuf rrbpum,obepull ull pmjylEllaom ta&oaulvpeprsm;ull wdk&tygon/ xi&haomom'utjzpf tpubaulw tolykri (armiarmi&qb 2012? 2-11/) Esh tajcpmvli, &&omrsm (armiarmi&qb 2009? 3/) jzplygon/

2? 1/ tpubaulwtolykri

rrbpum;obepull ull pmjylEllaom ta&oaulv peprsm;ull wdk&mw6f ysbmom pum;twuf ta&ygaom tohterhtjrihtwuftupeprsm;onfi a&stEd ta&peprsm;rStohtwlt&sniazmyaom oaulwvumujzihv&vmurh1/2yg/ rrbmom pum;\ wufusoh (Tone) rsm;ull ull pmjylEllaom tpubaulw peprsm;ull yswltwufcch ygon/ atmuygZ, m;(3)ullunhyg/

Z, m(3)o&oaulw wpt&wufi tolyj tpubaulw, 9lwEllaom (armiarmi&qb 2-11/)

	edjriob(1)	edjriob(2)	edjriob(3)	edjriob(4)	edjriob(5)
	ys-o&oaulw	atmuftpu wpt	, nab;tpu (2)c	, nab;(2)pu atmu(1)pu	, nab;tpu (3)c
t-o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	—	—	—	—	—
t#o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	~	~	~	~	
tk-o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	
	∩	∩			
	∩				
at-o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	
	∩	∩	∩	∩	
atm- o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	
	∩	∩	∩	∩	
	∩	∩	∩	∩	
t#o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	
t#o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	

	edfrib(1)	edfrib(2)	edfrib(3)	edfrib(4)	edfrib(5)
	yl-o& oauw	atmutpuf wptk	, mab;tpuf (2)ck	, mab;(2)puf atmu(1)puf	, mab;tpuf (3)ck
edfriblytpuf oauwrs;					
t#o&oauw\ edfriblytpuf oauwrs;	ḡ	ḡ	ḡ:		
	ḡ	ḡ			

azmfyygZ, m;t& ylw\bmompum;onf toerrih t&nftaoG ig;rdtxd
 ½Mumif tpubauw ta&pepft& oElygon/ wufusobmompum; (Tone
 language) toMiykaom vr&jzpbMumif, cllrmpbn azmfyElygon/

2? 2/ tajcpmvNi , h&;omri

rtfpm;oppeful ul fm;jyEhaom ta&oauwpeprsm;ul wlxGc&mwGf tjcm;
 tEd pmta&;tom;wlvGf raw&aom pmMumif tajcu pmvNi , h&;rsn a&;omrlul
 aw&ygon/ jreEmEli h&stapmyll fym&s fsm;u jAm [pmvHrsn; [qMuygon/ xyrsvf
 a&;om;rsn;ygOihai jAm [pmvHrsn; r [kvlyg/ ydpmvHrsn;omjzplyd t&G ftpm;
 xuDurG , hatmi h&;xm;jcifom jzplygon/ atmuylgZ, m;(4)uMunlyg/

Z, m(4) tajcpmvNi , h&;omxmri

pOf	ausupmtrnf	rf&qumv	tu&mylumelwtsuf
1	[elvifoc&fys ausupm	at' (3)	
2	rllfarmjre' ylausupm	at' (3)	
3	oulefylausupm	at' (4)	
4	ueDuacgifiulef?aiGukvf	at' (4)	

pwlvnt pmMumif tajcu&;jci? rlvpmvHxuf xuDurG , jci? rlvpmvH
 E&ctMum; a&;av&jci? tpubauwlygvGf xlbauw atmuwG h&;jci? [hom
 tajctaersm;amumih t-owbabm [hom , qrrsm;vnf ½Elygon/ ohomf
 xlbauw pmvHrsn;onf rlvtoE&ctS wptcES h ajjyppbn qupyhaom oabmuH
 aw&ygon/ tqMAsnfoabm ouDihaonh taetxm;jzplygon/ tqMAsnfoH
 ygaom bmompum; [kr&f,qElygon/ (armi hmi h&qG 2009? 13/)

azmfyygoabmt& ydpmwlvf vnf, xlyrsw&om; rsm; ygOim? t [lufxlyrswf [k
 qEh haom xlyrswrsm; ygOihaygon/ xlr squvuzBzlvmaom Bwfbklyrswrsm; vnf,
 ygOihaygon/ xhumi fyd pmta&tom;wof [elvifocsh fpmont [luf xlyrswESh
 rOfwlyrswf a&maxfygOiharhalmumi haw&orOySurh fpmrsm;wof tapmqh [krsvf, h
 ygon/ atmulygyLunlyg/

y(1) [elvifocsh fpm

xhaemufaw&aom ydpmwlvf t [lufxlyrswf rsm;ubm tohlykalmumif, aw&yg onf/
 azmfychaom Z, m;(4)rSylrsm; uhlunh&avlmEhlygon/

(2) tfo&oauw xlycmrl

ydpm ta&tom;wof tfo&onlvnf, xlycm;aom ta&ofyijzplygon/ ydpmwof
 tfo&uhtu&mjzih] } a&om;avhlyb? Asnf, Dfo& oauwul] } } oauw jzih
 a&avhlygon/ (armi harmi hq 2010? 13/)

ohom&stEd ta&tom;rsm;wof azmfyavh&aom o&shb&oauw tfo&tu&ESh
 tfo&Asnf, Dfo& oauwulhl ydpmwof tohlykrhaw&yg/ (onjrw? 1958? 4/)

(3) tko&oauw xlycmrl

xhtwtko&a&om;rEShywbouf vnf, xlycm;rsm;aw&yg onf/ ydpmwof tko&uht
 tu&mjzih] } } a&om;avhlyb? Asnf, Dfo& oauwul] } } oauw rsm;jzih
 a&avhlygon/ (armi harmi hq 2006? 15/)

ohomf a&stEd ta&tom;rsm;wof azmfyavh&aom o&shb&oauw tfo&tu&ESh
 ESht-Asnf, Dfo& oauwulhl ydpmwof tohlykrhaw&yg/ pwofqhbnf rsh
 o&shb&ESh ta&pepf rsh [qjicfr [kwlyg/ , ifo&shb& oauwul a&stEd
 ta&tom;rsm;ubv -a&cpepf v&udwifqtwpepf E&facsmifiipeprsm; jzihrohcif
 ubmqhlygon/ Z, m;(3)wof azmfyxm;aompeprsm;EShwluqhl avhlymyg/

jAm [dtu& ta&tom;zbzrl avhlmcsursm;t&vnf ydpm\ uylm;aom ta&
 ofyifullawqriEhlygon/

Z, m (6) jAm[t u&nESfta&;tom, z&hrylyZ, m

pmv	jAm[P	uk/ef	tEd ajrmuyll f			tEd avmi yll f			yl
	BC-3	AD-2	AD-3	AD-4	AD-7	AD-3	AD-4	AD-5	AD-3
um	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	
ud	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ
ud	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	
uk	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ
ul	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	
au	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ
aum	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ

Z, m; t& (t) o&r&ritpubaukvjzplf ajymi f,vh r 1/2 yg/ (tm? at? atm) o&w&r&n vnfr&of&ajzmi ES hr&of&h&zplu&v&on&rst y x&jcm; aom ajymi f,vh raw&yg/ o&omf (t& t) ES h (tr t) o&rsm; onf acwftvlu f vub&; p 1/2 u&ajymi f,vh 1/2 yg onf (t& t& tr t) a&; x&rsm; onf ajrmuyll f tu&m? avmi yll f tu&m oabmwlyg O i 1/2 r u acwftvlu f u&v&u&umif,vnf Z, m; t&jri&aw&E&lygonf/ Z, m;(6) \ aemu f q& aumf v&w&f y&o&oau f w a&; om; r&peprsm; u& azm f y x m; &m tEd ajrmuyll f? avmi yll f ta&; tom; w&ES h u&ym; jcm; em; aom u& yll peprsm; ES tom 1/2 &ech&umif aw&ri&E&lygonf onf

(4) jAm[t u&r&S at '(2-3) cell of u&vpr&f

yl&w&on&pmta&; tom; u& a&S tEd ta&; tom; r&, &mw&f tu&m w&N taetxm; t& tEd ajrmuyll f a' o pmta&; tom; w&S t&jcc&, b&f ewlygonf/ tal&umif r&n y&tu&m w&N of yiftaetxm; rsm; onf ajrmuyll f tEd tu&m w&ES h a, b& s oabmw&e&jcif jzplygonf/ Z, m;(1) u&N unlyg/

o&mw&f jAm[t u&m w&N ajrmuyll f to&f u&rsm; ES hvnf xyw&h&v&h&f r 1/2 yg/ tu&mt&of rsm; uyif ajrmuyll f tu&mt&of rsm; ES h w&h&f 1/2 yg/ at' (2) &mpk ajrmuyll f ubeta&; tom; w&ES h tu&my&rsm; cyqiqi 1/2 yg/? Asnf, Dfo& a&; q&f rsm; w&f jcm; em; onf tx&ojzi h Asnf, Dfo&]-] ES h Asnf, Dfo&]-] a&; om; r&rsm; w&f xi&f&n;

azmfyrhsm; onf tu&myht & r&fqrjy/kxm; jci fom jzplygon/ pumv w&f y&spmrsm; u&ll
 a&usupmw&ll f&sm; w&ll b&mr u ai &xnfy p&nf? tkw&csy? w&ll q&ll w&ll w&ll v&nf, aw&ll y&gon/
 Z, m; (8) u&ll unlyg/

Z, m(8) y&spmt rsm; q&ll w&ll a&om u&mv r&f y&spmrsm

pOf	a&usupmtrnf	r&f q&umv	tu&myht u&muElw&csul
1	oa&aw&mf o&ll d O&ll ur r&ll &ll m; t 1/2 t 1/2 at mu&ll f&su E&ll n y&ll pm	at' (4-5)	
2	oa&acw&mf ci b&u&ll e&ll f? ai &ll u&ll kv (at mu&ll f&em;)	at' (5-6)	
3	oa&acw&mf ai &ll y&ll v&ll h? y&ll pm	at' (5-6)	
4	[e&ll v&ll i? O&ll b&ll a&ll q&ll mi f, m? y&ll a&ll u&ll s&ll u&ll p&ll m	at' (5-6)	
5	oa&acw&mf O&ll b&ll O&ll m P&ll r&ll mi f&ll v&ll s&ll y&ll a&ll u&ll s&ll u&ll p&ll m	at' (6-7)	
6	o&ll p&ll n&ll t&ll r&ll e, ? q&ll i &ll n y&ll a&ll u&ll s&ll u&ll p&ll m	at' (6-&)	
7	oa&acw&mf ue O&ll u&ll a&ll c&ll g&ll i f, u&ll e&ll f? y&ll -ou&ll w&ll e&ll b, y&ll pm	at' (6-&)	
8	oa&acw&mf b&ll &ll m&ll a&ll x&ll mi f&ll t 1/2 t 1/2 y&ll pm	at' (6-7)	
9	oa&acw&mf ri f&ll w&ll u&ll e&ll f y&ll a&ll u&ll s&ll u&ll p&ll m w&ll f	at' (6-7)	
10	ai &ll t&ll t&ll z&ll h	at' (4) a&em u&ll y&ll f	
11	oa&acw&ll m aj&ll r&ll w&ll q&ll y&ll v&ll h&ll r&ll sm;?	at' (4) a&em u&ll y&ll f	
12	oa&acw&ll mt kv&ll c&ll p&ll m&ll r&ll sm;?	at' (4) a&em u&ll y&ll f	

azmfyygumvty&ll f&ll t&ll j&ll cm; (at' (4)&mpc&ll e&ll f&ll s (at' (7)&mpc&ll e&ll b&ll n f&ll y&ll a&ll c&ll w&ll \ p&ll may&ll t&ll a&ll ;
 tom; trsm; q&ll w&ll a&ll o&ll m u&ll mv t&ll j&ll z&ll p&ll r&ll e&ll q&ll e&ll ll y&ll gon/ y&ll spmay&ll z&ll b&ll z&ll r&ll umv [k q&ll v&ll y&ll g
 onf

(3) acwlyl bompum? pmt a&t omwESjcmemaejci f

yswlonf rrbompum;twuf yspmull wlxictuaomvntf rrbompum;Esh
 acwlyl jzpaom tjc;bompum;rsn;twluul rrt\ ystun? yspmta&pepfull
 tolyla&om;rtjylyg/ rrtwvucthcom bmojcm;pum;\ rvtun? ta&pep
 twll f &, la&om;avlygon/ Z, m;(9)uunlyg/

Z, m;(9) acwlyl bompum? pmt a&t omwESH Ellf, Sjyxmri

r&f q umv	y t u&myk (y l b m o m t w l u)	*k a' Oem* & D t u&myk (o u w b m o m t w l u)	t E d awmi yll f t u&myk sm; (y g V b m o m t w l u)
at' 0 (2-3)			
	[e v i f ? o c s f y s p m		
at' 0 (3)			
	rll farm? jre' y s p m		
at' 0 (3-4)			
	oulef? ysaumupm		
at' 0 (4-5)			
	oa&acw&m? b&m;Bud t 1/2 t? atmucthsuEh? y s p m		
at' 0 (5-6)			
	oa&acw&m? ci boulef? ai Ukwl? y s p m/	oa&acw&m? jri lom [k b&m; Xmyemvlu? q i f w y v i b o u w p m/	oa&acw&m? ci boulef? ai Ukwl? y g V b m o m/
at' 0 (5-6)			
	[e v i f ? O b a q m i f , m y s p m	& c h l a O o m v h c w f o u w p m	o a & a c w & m ? w l f n y j l r l l a y g u l y g V b m o m /
at' 0 (6-7)			
	o a & a c w & m ? u e D u a c j i f u l e f ? y v i y w v n l y s p m /	o a & a c w & m ? u e D u a c j i f u l e f ? y v i f y w v n l o u w p m /	o a & a c w & m ? b & m ; B u d t e b ? a u s m u p m o h y l l f u s t ? y g V b m o m /

refq umv	y1 tu&myM (y1bmomtWu)	*y1 a' Oem* & Dt u&myM (ouwvbmomtWu)	tEd awmi y1 f tu&myM sm; (ygVbmomtWu)
at' 0 (6-7)			
	oa&acw&m? b&m; axmi f t 1/2 t 1/2 yw/vn? y1pm/	&cM P a0omv h cw/! ouwvpm	oa&cw&m? ci l bulef? a&ayvM? ygVbmom/
at' 0 (7-8)			
	oa&acw&m? b&m; Bu0t 1/2 t 1/2 t 1/2? ab; yw/vn? y1pm/	&cM P a0omv h cw/! ouwvpm (a' Oem* & Dt u&m)	, cM f E M f (a&S r E w M f)' M &M0w h cw/! ygVbmom/ (rEft u&m)
at' 0 (7-8)			
	oa&acw&m? b&m; Bu0t 1/2 t 1/2? ab; yw/vn? y1pm/		
at' 0 (7-8)			
	oa&acw&m? b&m; Bu0t 1/2 t 1/2 t 1/2? ab; yw/vn? y1pm		a u s m u B u 0 t M l l e, P u l e f, q y & M? y g V b m o m /
at' 0 (11)			
	(j r p o m; N r M l a w 0) y k' h c w / a p m v t; r i f a u s m u p m? y 1 p m /	(j r p o m; N r M l a w 0) y k' h c w / a p m v t; r i f a u s m u p m? o u w v p m (e m * & D t u & m)	(j r p o m; N r M l a w 0) y k' h c w / a p m v t; r i f a u s m u p m? y g V b m o m /
at' 0 (11)			
	y k' N r M l a & q h w m l o b & m; ? t k w f c l u h a u s m? y 1 p m		
at' 0 (11)			
	y k' N r M l a & q h w m l o b & m; ? t k w f c l u h a u s m? y 1 p m		
at' 0 (12)			
	y k' N r M l a & m Z u l m & h a u s m u p m? y 1 p m /		y k' N r M l a & m Z u l m & f a u s m u p m? y g V b m o m /

r&f; q umv	y< tu&myk (y<bmomt w<u)	*y< a' Oem* & D tu&myk (ou<wvbmomt w<u)	tEd awmi y< f tu&myk sm; (ygv<bmomt w<u)
at' ̣ (12)			 yk' ̣ a&f' Bu< b&m;? ygv<bmom/

azmfyyga&; x<rl aumuEkw<sur sm; t& ou<wvbmom a&; x<rl sm; ul at' (5)
 &mp<dekusi fuyif &cl' a' ou< aOomv<cw<f ou<w ur<h<fpmr sm; 1/2 ygon/ *y<
 tu&mul to<h<yk<ly< at' (7) &mpk aemu y< f w<f a' Oem* & D tu&mjzih a&; om; c<lu
 ygon/ oa&acw<mw<f v<n<f; x<bu<wv bompum; a&; x<rl 1/2 E< m a&mu< 1/2 maom
 r< i< f tu& m ta&; tom; jzpaom *y< At u&mjzih y< if a&; om; x< m; ygon/

]]y< & Z, (ou<w) w<ly< E< (y<)}}
 #

y(2) ueDu<h<cgif u<f ou<wv- y< e< b, pmaumuEkw<sur

azmfyygyw<v<f ou<wvpmv<mul *y< At u&mjzih a&; om; ly<? y< pmv<mul y< tu&mjzih
 a&; om; x< m; ygon/ ur<h<fpmv<pw<ckv<n<f; y< yif bompum; u< f ym; on< f t av< u< f tu&
 to< f v<n<f; c< f cm; to< h< yk< x< m; a< lu mi f; aw< & ygon/

x<lt w< ygv<bmom a&; x<rl w<v<f v<n<f; ygv<ES h y< tu& m? y< pmta&; tom; ES h
 to< f u< f ym; r< ul aw< & ygon/ ci bai u< kw< w< f ygv< a&; om; r< lü -

y(3) ci bai u< kw< f ygv< pm (yv< 0 tu& m)

[hom tEd awmi y< f yv< 0 tu& m? ta&; o< f yif u< l aw< & ygon/ x< h< i u< kw< l yif
 y< pma&; x<rl ü-

y(4) ci bai u< kw< f y< pm (y< t u& m)

[hom y< tu& m? ta&; o< f yif u< l aw< & ygon/ x< lt yif y< w< l ygv< pma&; om; r< lü
 y< acw< f u< mv< pw< ckv< n< f; y< yif ygv< bmomu< l tu& m tr< r< t jzih a&; om; on< f y< tu& m
 ta&; pepu< h< v< 0 to< h< r< yk< y/

Z, m(10)ygVurhfpmt oftrsr#

p0f	urhfpmtrnf	tu&my#
1	oa&acw&m? ci lbulef? ai DuKv? ygVp/m/	
2	oa&acw&m? w0 fNy/rhlaygu? ygVp/m/	
3	oa&acw&m? b&m;Bu0 te0?ausnupmohy# f,ust? ygVp/m/	
4	oa&cw&m?ci lbulef? a&ayv#? ygVp/m/	
5	ausnubun#le, ? uef,qy&0? ygVp/m/	

azmfyyg aw0#ft& ysa'ow0f ygVpmtw0f y#tu&mpmta&;tom;ul ro#b
r#v#vuc#&m tEd awmif#f ta&;tu& wpr#str#ul to#y#l#umif azmfyE#f yg
onf

x#ub#om a&;om;r#p#f#ul y#acw#v#omru y#acw#v#umv jz#om
y#acw#v# t#y#i#&#bnf[kq#E#f ygonf/ p#on#ul j#r#p#om;#r#l# ayawmulefausni f, w#l#f
r#aw#om ou&mZi 441 x#? apm#v#r#i#facw#ausnupm (armi#armi#q# 2014? 2-13/
u ou#ox#v#ul #ygonf/

**y#(5) j#r#p#om;#r#l# ayawmulefausni f#w#l#f#aw#om ou&mZi441x#?
apm#v#r#i#facw#ausnupm**

tqHAsnf,of[k r, lqEHfyg/ xhMumi h tqHAsnf,of a&;om;ri[k r&f,qaomy&pmrS
 tajcpmvhi , frsm;onf acwNyhi f OP&Nywf pum;olrsm; vfr&hramumi h ta&;uG t[ef
 wvavon/ xhMumi h tajcpmvhrygaom y&pmta&;tom;rsm;uH y&pmayacw&Ehi fyH f
 ta&tom; [kqHfygon/ aumuEkv&azny&aomf -

Z, m(11) y&pmay acw&Ehi fyH f ta&tom

pof	urhif,pmtrni	r&fqumv	tu&myH
1	oa&acw&mf b&m;bu&th&tH?	at' (7-8)	
2	oa&acw&mf b&m;bu&th&tH?	at' (7-8)	
3	oa&acw&mf b&m;bu&th&tH?	at' (7-8)	
4	[e v i f? em;½ef,uef taemurS y&pm/	at' (8-9)	
4	(jrp&om;h&law&)y&kHcw? apmvtri fausupm? y&pm/	at' (11)	
5	y&kH& o&ygw&tg;rS w½kvpmausmbuygaom y&pm/	at' (11)	
6	y&kH&a&tq&hw&mb&m;? tkv&cluf ausm? y&pm/	at' (11)	
7	y&kH& &mZur&fausupm? y&pm/	at' (12)	

[li aw&EHfygon/

Z, m;tr&vpOf (1? 2? 3)onf oa&acw&mrjzplyb? at' (7-8)&mpk[k r&f,qaomy&pmrS
 [e v i f w&lvnf e*g;½ef,uef taemulbur&aw&om y&pmonf tajc pmvhi , frygaom
 ta&;tom;jzplon/ umvtm;jzih at' (8-9) [k , m, r&f,qaomy&pmrS; r&f
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 a&g&hr&ixm;í (11)&mpk[k aznyygon/ &mZur&fxuf apmonf[k , lq&aom
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 y&pmta&;tom;uH olrsm; at' (7-8)&mpk aemu&fyH frSy&kHcw&v&at mi f tajcpmvhi , f

rygaom yspmta&tom;uH tolykMualumi; aEhif;ta&om;fyi pepful awU&yg on/ yspm ta&tom;qH &m orH; taxmuftxm;wpcktzpvnf; rsvf, Ehl ygon/

yKhcwif rE? jrefm? ygVd -pmta&tom;rs;Esh yspm

yKhcwionf yspmarSrelybaemurS jyelvnawU&vm&aom tajctaejzpbnf/ xLumv yspmwf acwlyH bompum;wH vfr;Hrsm; ouDivU&yg on/ xHlumi h acwlyH rE? jrefmEsh ywH tu&m? pmta&tom; qupyrbabmrsm;uH azmfj vlygon/

(1) rEpmta&tom;Esh yKhcwifEhausupm? tu&myH

at' (8) &mpDef;usi wof , ckh;Ehif; e, hjrtwof; avmb&D y&yxH a&Srla [mi; rsm;u-a&Srehausupm? ygVausupmrsm;uH tEd awmiyH tofrsm; rS & , b&om; ta&tom;w;zih a&om;xm;yg on/ a&Srebmomjzih a&om;xm;aom rehausupm rsm;jzpygon/ tEd awmiyH tofrsm;uH & , h&om;xm;ly? xHsvpqifwufum yKhcwifrepm ta&tom;rs; zHkvm[e/lygon/ Z, m;(12)uHunlyg/

Z, m(12) a&Srepm tu&myH

pOf	urH;pmtrnf	re&umv	urH;tu&myH
1	'&nowD y&yxH rehausupm a&Sreft u&m	at' (8) Def;usif	ဇာတိဗျာဓိဗျာဓိ
2	'&nowD y&yxH rehausupm a&Sreft u&m	at' (8) Def;usif	ဗျာဓိဗျာဓိ နံဗြာဓိဗျာဓိ
3	'&nowD y&yxH rehausupm a&Sreft u&m	at' (8) Def;usif	ဇာတိဗျာဓိဗျာဓိ
4	jrpom;aywmuf? (apmv;ri;vufwuf) ausupm? reft u&m	at' (11)	
5	yKhcwif ueppom;ri; twlyvhausupm reft u&m	at' (11)	
6	jynit a&Iqhwf b&m;rehausupm? reft u&m (yKhcwif)	at' (11)	
7	yKhcwif &Zurmf rehausupm? reft u&m	at' (12)	

tEd awmiyH; ta&tom;wH tajccl' &nowDhcwif repm ta&tom;rs; zHkvm[xHs tu&mtofi qupyrl taetxm;t& yKhcwifrepm? reft u&m ta&tom;rs; quvuzHkvm[e/lygon/

(2) jrefmpmta&;tomtpo&fyiEShr&ftu&mta&;tomqubpyrl

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 jr [me&h&evu&f&e& } [h&ompum;v&rs& jzpygon/ x&ub& jrefmpum;v&rs;u&f
 prf&oy&;om;r&rs;½&om&vnt? at' (11)&mplavmuftxd jrefmpmta&;tom;u&f
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 Z, m;tw&f&f av&h&v&mlun&f&lygon/

Z, m(13)y&f&h&cw&r&ftjrefmt u&rs&E&f, D&f

pOf	ausupmtrnf	a&;x&umv	r&ft u&my&f
1	jrpb&ayw&ulef? (apmv&ri&fv&u&w&u) ausupm;r&ft u&f	at' (11)	
2	y&f&h& usepp&om;ri&f tw&fy&v&ausupm r&ft u&f	at' (11)	
3	jyn&f&a&f&aw&mf b&rs;r&h&ausupm? r&ft u&f (y&f&h&cw&f)	at' (11)	
4	y&f&h&rs&Z&ur&m&f ausupm? r&ft u&f	at' (12)	
5	y&f&h&ay&aw&mf&b&rs; ausupm? jrefmt u&f	at' (12) Oef&usif	
6	y&f&h&rs&Z&ur&m&f ausupm? jrefmt u&f	at' (12)	

ay:aw&mf&f&ta&;tom;of&fyi&ft& &m&Z&ur&m&f&x&uf& rs; p&h&rapm&E&f&lyg/ av&mi&cp&n&b&f&f
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 n&f&w&rr&½&f&ic&f&al&umi&hou&m&Z&f&f&rm&rl tm;enf&f& rs; p&h&rapm&E&f&f&on&h&taetxm; r&½&f&f&om
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 ayaw&ma&us&mf& apmv&ri&f&v&u&x&uf& ausupm&v&f&f& jrefmpmta&;tom; v&h&O ryg&O&f&f&ic&f&u?
 ou&h&oc&h&eoavm [k , l&rd&f&gon/ &m&Z&ur&m&f&om&v&f&f& ou&m&Z&f&f& t&cl&f&f&rm&yg&om
 tapmq& jrefmpmta&;tom;jzpb&ae&j&f&f&f& y&f&f& c&f&f&maeygon/

(3) jrefmt u&myl tu&myl jcmemrlt ajctae

azmfyobnft wll f a&S0bjrefmtu&mojfyiul tu&myl rsm; qubyrft & r&w&xlts & clbnf [baom tp0ft vmazmfyrbnf cl rfmvsul / ygon/ obomf yk jrefmES h acwlyl f umvwlf jrefmES h rwhbaom yltu&mojfyi f 1/2aeonful & mZurm&f ausmupmu oubaoxlvul / ygon/

Z, m(14) jrefmpmt u&myl h yspmt u&myl jcmemrl

1	yK& mZurm&f ausmupm? ytl u&myl	at' (12)	
2	yK& mZurm&f ausmupm? ygl/bmomt u&myl	at' (12)	
3	yK& mZurm&f ausmupm? r&ft u&myl	at' (12)	
4	yK& mZurm&f ausmupm? jrefmt u&myl	at' (12)	

azmfyygZ, m; t& r&? ygVl jrefmwll pmta& tom; toG rfn wpr&wnf [k rsvf, Ell f avmu&tmif whaeonful aw&ygon/ ysrn qubyr&avmu&tmif toG lue onful jri&w&ae&ygon/ x&llumi h yk wvlf yslw&aeon/ jrefmES h rwhbaom oDjcm; jzpa&eonh yspum; ul ajymq&cl elwlygon/ yspmu&vnf a&c&nu [elwlygon/ xlt w&ul yk acwft xdl yslw&bnf jrefmajrrfn v&st&pkvp&ct jzpf & ylvn&clbnf [k , lqrd ygon/

jcll b&oytsuf

(1) yslpmta& tom; ul at' (2) & mp&clw&f a&st&ed ajrmu&lyl f? awmi&lyl f jAm [P tu&myl ta& tom; ul f rsm; ubl jAm [tu&myl ta& tom; ul f wpr&ct jzpf yslw&, clcif ES h yslw&bnf tq&an&fol&om wufus&h b&ompum wpr&cl ul ajymq&lyl? jrefmajray: rS jrefmwll rwh&clbaom v&om; r&st&EG pkvp&ct jzpf azmfy Ell ygon/

(2) yslw&bnf pmta& tom; twwul a&st&ed om; w&xlts & 1/2&lyl? r&clbom pum; tw&ul jlylyize&w&? w&xlts rsm; jzi h a& om; c&nu on/ at' (3-4) & mp&clw&f pwif z&cl&vmon/ at' (4-7) & mp&clw&f w&fus, p&h toG y&aeonful aw&ygon/ at' (7-9) & mp&clw&f acwlyl f b&ompum; rsm; \ v&fr&llumi h ta& tom; ajymi fvl vml y&aeomu? at' (9-11) & mp&clw&f yslpmta& tom; aw&xlts r taxmuft xm; enfyg; i? tmenf vmaom pmta& tom; tjzpf rsvf, Ell ygon/

(3)at' (11-12)&mpLum;w0f yk'k'cwlydpm aw&jci;fallumi h xllumvtxdydvrd;
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 onlv'f ydtu&m? ydpm'ta&;pep'ull jrefmtu&m? jrefmp'm'ta&;pep'oll rajymi;f;cl
 r&ftu&m? r&ep'm'ta&;pep'ulbm jrefmtu&m? jrefmp'm'ta&;pep'oll ajymi;f;v'clLumi f
 aw'ljric&ygon/

edH

azmfyygtallumi f rsm'nf ydpm ydtu&m'w'ull tajcjy'ki uEly'f'v'hm'cl'om ola'woe
 rsm;u'li p'pn'f;um'wi'f'x'm;jci'f;jzpygon/ av'lv'm'r'k'v'p'c'k'v'ull azmfy&on'ft w'ul
 em;v'n'r'c'ub'c'j'ci'f paom t'cu'ft'c'hrsm; ½&v'm'Ellygon/ x'lt'w'ul v'm'a&mu'f'a'q'G'a'Es'j'ci'f
 ar;jref'j'ci'f'rsm; j'y'Ellygon/ aumi'faom t'bu'j'y'k'r'sm;u'lv'nt; v'uc'li bu'k'p'm;ob;
 ygrn/ qu'lv'ul ydpmay? yd'bmompum;? yd'ta&;tom;rsm;Esh r&ep'may? r&el'bmom
 pum; r&efta&;tom;rsm;u'li oi'num;a&;taxmu'ft'ujz'p&ef bu'k'y'r'f'a'q'mi &u'lo'ob;r'ni
 jzpygon/

ur'f'ul'p'm&i'f

pl'bm'a't'mi' 00/ (1974)/ **at' 'Bjcmu&mpEsh i'f'rw'if'f'cl'f'yn'b'lt'u&m'** &elule! Or'f'a't'mi' p'may/
 azarmi'lv'i' 00/ (1958)/ **bmomavmu'ur'f'** &elule'p'm? ay'Ar'm'e'y'El'y'w'ul/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' 00/ (2006)/ **y'd'p'm'ta&;tom'r's'r's An'f, 0b& (t'p t)toH** jyn'lv'u'ob'lv'
 jref'm'p'm'x'm'e'w'0'f'z'w'ul'm;aom ola'woe'p'm'w'rf'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' armi'v' (2006)/ **jref'm'El'li'k'j'ur'ih'f'p'm's'r's ydtu&mo'P'h'e'r's'Es'h yd'p'm'v'
 a&;omy'p'ep'f'm'av'lv'm'c'sul** 2006-yg&*l'ob'ur'f? &elule'lv'u'ob'lv'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' a'gu'lv'm/ 2009/ **[[y'd'p'm'umi'f'tajc'f'p'm'v'li, f'm'av'lv'm'r']** Journal of Myanmar
 Academy of Arts and Science. Vol.No.7-B, pm53-67/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' 2009/ **y'd'p'm'umi'f'tajc'f'p'm'v'li, f'm'av'lv'm'c'sul** &elule! jref'm'El'li' H O'z'AE's'io'y'h
 t'z'ob'lv'wi'ob'f'aom ola'woe'p'm'w'rf'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' a'gu'lv'm/ (2010)/ **u'el'q'f'y'g'lv'au's'up'm'r'a&Stu&mo'0'f'y'if'sm av'lv'm c'sul**
 jyn'lv'w' jyn'lv'u'ob'lv'ob'lv'wi'ob'f'aom ola'woe'p'm'w'rf'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' (2010)/ **y'd'p'm'ta&;tom'r's'r'An'f, 0b& (t'p t) toH** &elule! jref'm'El'li' H O'z'AE's' h
 o'y'h't'z'ob'lv'wi'ob'f'aom ola'woe'p'm'w'rf'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' (2012)/ **y'd'p'm'ta&;o'0'f'y'if's'p'ub'au'lv't'o'f'r'm/** &elule! jref'm'El'li' H O'z'AE's' h o'y'h
 t'z'ob'lv'wi'ob'f'aom ola'woe'p'm'w'rf'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' a'gu'lv'm/ (2014)/ **j'r'p'om'lv'hyaw'm'aus'ni'f? au's'up'm'aw'm'i'bu'f r'su'El'0?
 tu&my'lv'm'av'lv'm'c'sul** a&Sa[mi'f'ola'woe'Es'h t'r'cl'om;jy'w'lv'u'ob'p'0' Xme/ p'm'w'rf;z'w'y'f's
 ola'woe'p'm'w'rf'/

om'j'r'w'f' 00 (o'0'y's't') (1963)/ **y'z'w'p'm'** &elule! ti'lv'm'ae'&S'e, v'

	BC-1	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜
Northern Indian Scripts	AD-2	𑀓𑀲	𑀓𑀳	𑀕𑀲	𑀕𑀳	𑀗𑀲	𑀗𑀳	𑀙𑀲	𑀙𑀳	𑀛𑀲	𑀛𑀳
	AD-4	𑀓𑀴	𑀓𑀵	𑀕𑀴	𑀕𑀵	𑀗𑀴	𑀗𑀵	𑀙𑀴	𑀙𑀵	𑀛𑀴	𑀛𑀵
	AD-7	𑀓𑀶	𑀓𑀷	𑀕𑀶	𑀕𑀷	𑀗𑀶	𑀗𑀷	𑀙𑀶	𑀙𑀷	𑀛𑀶	𑀛𑀷
Southern Indian Scripts	AD-3	𑀓𑀸	𑀓𑀹	𑀕𑀸	𑀕𑀹	𑀗𑀸	𑀗𑀹	𑀙𑀸	𑀙𑀹	𑀛𑀸	𑀛𑀹
	AD-4	𑀓𑀺	𑀓𑀻	𑀕𑀺	𑀕𑀻	𑀗𑀺	𑀗𑀻	𑀙𑀺	𑀙𑀻	𑀛𑀺	𑀛𑀻
	AD-6	𑀓𑀼	𑀓𑀽	𑀕𑀼	𑀕𑀽	𑀗𑀼	𑀗𑀽	𑀙𑀼	𑀙𑀽	𑀛𑀼	𑀛𑀽
Pyu Script	AD-3	𑀓𑀾		𑀕𑀾		𑀗𑀾		𑀙𑀾		𑀛𑀾	
	AD-5	𑀓𑀿		𑀕𑀿		𑀗𑀿		𑀙𑀿		𑀛𑀿	
	AD-12	𑀓𑀿		𑀕𑀿		𑀗𑀿		𑀙𑀿		𑀛𑀿	
Mon Script	AD-12	𑀓𑀿	𑀓𑀿	𑀕𑀿	𑀕𑀿	𑀗𑀿	𑀗𑀿	𑀙𑀿	𑀙𑀿	𑀛𑀿	𑀛𑀿

PL Gupta Acient & Medieval Indian Alphabets Tables; yk yif, ? tif0? jrefm
 aumuxif,tu&myrsm;? 1979? aemuquwZ, m;rsn;/ IG-Guhler, 1904, Indian
 Palaeography; D. Dinger, 1949, The Alphabets; B. Pandey, 1957, Indian Palaeography;
 ODomjrw? 1963? yszwpm/ ODr? 1961? jrefmtu&njzphay:vmyW ODomjrw? 1956?
 reJrefmtu&morif/ ODrkmatmi? 1974? 6- &mpES h ifrwi r&cifjynbH tu&m
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